

Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine
Department of Mathematics

**A Quantitative Approach to
Non-Deliverable Forwards**

Market Microstructure Features, Risk-Management
and Algorithmic Applications

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First a warning, musical; then the hour, irrevocable.
The leaden circles dissolved in the air.
- Virginia Woolf, *Mrs. Dalloway*

To my family, and to my dearest friends.

Abstract

Increase in Non-Deliverable Forwards volumes in the past two years has led to structural changes in this market. We examine in this MSc thesis the current market microstructure and suggest risk-management methods. Algorithmic applications are presented, in line with current regulatory requirements.

Our analysis reveals a market with different regimes throughout the day characterized by liquidity and volatility. We simulate pricing for underlying NDF spot rate with CIR and Vasicek models and our GARCH methodology for volatility forecasting leads to satisfactory results.

Keywords Futures, NDFs, Algorithms, Vasicek, CIR, GARCH

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Preface

Foreign exchange products have always been at the heart of financial activities. As the pace of globalization increases and as investors are more eager to invest abroad after the financial crisis, many of these assets have known a sharp rise in traded volumes.

In a climate of growing political and economic uncertainty, especially in Asia, investors are keen to invest in a future contract to protect themselves against fluctuations of interest rates. One of these contracts is the Non-Deliverable Forward (NDF). The latter is mainly used by developing countries in Asia and Latin America.

Although NDFs have been traded since the end of the 1990s, their volumes have now significantly increased in the past two years. The London Clearing House reports a 1100% increase over the past two years, with strong growth on Asian currencies [1]. This has led to substantial investments in the field of trading automation related to NDFs in the past year.

I have chosen to present as my MSc thesis a quantitative approach to the NDFs market. These assets are now at a turning point: still inherently a voice market, but with an increasing number of electronic participants, it displays features one may expect from both. I have been throughout this project very excited by the fast-changing environment around this asset class.

Firstly, we will take a very close look at the market microstructure of non-deliverable forwards. An overview of the price formation process, based on Lehalle's *Market Microstructure in Practice* [12], will help us introduce the fundamental drivers of the different liquidity pools available at the time this thesis is written.

Secondly, we will explore different ways to approach risk management of NDFs. This will include a pricing methodology based on implicit NDF spot rate, which we will then simulate using Vasicek and CIR models. We will also use GARCH modeling for volatility forecasting and derive Value at Risk and Expected Shortfall.

Finally, we will take a glimpse into the most up to date electronic strategies from a quantitative perspective. After reviewing specific theoretical concept, mostly based on Chen's *Algorithmic Trading: Winning Strategies and Their Rationale* [8], I will give an overview of simulator design and basic algorithmic structures one can use on this specific market.

Part I

Market Microstructure

Chapter 1

Overview of the Price Formation Process

This section is highly inspired by Lehalle's book *Market microstructure in practice* [12].

1.1 Introduction

In 2002, Bouchaud [6] described the price dynamics as a result of the order book and the order flow. Thus, the Price formation process can be analyzed as follows [12]. Once a deal is fulfilled, one can observe a spike in the price, materializing the deal impact. There is the decay of the price towards what the investor believes is the fair value.

1.2 Liquidity

Fragmentation In order to monitor the fragmentation of the market, market share for trading venues is commonly used [12] A common result is that fragmentation increases when liquidity increases. We can, however, notice there are two types of liquidity [12]:

- A natural liquidity, which is due to medium and long-term investors.
- An opportunistic liquidity, due to high-frequency traders.

MiFID [12] has implemented high pre-trade and post-trade transparency. This means that once a deal is settled, the information should be published after a certain delay. This allows for more transparency in the transactions and helps to monitor the state of the market. There are several kinds of pools from which an investor can choose. Dark pools are preferred when there is a significant transaction since they only publish minimal data. The use of dark pools also protects the identity of the transaction parties, most of the time. Exchanges are also required to publish their best execution policy.

Measuring fragmentation One of the most intuitive ways to measure fragmentation is to use entropy, which is already commonly used in Physics. For a product traded on N

venues, the normalized entropy can be written as follows.

$$H = -\frac{1}{\log N} \sum_{i=1}^N M_i \log M_i \quad (1.1)$$

where M_i is the market share of the i th venue [12].

Why fragmentation matters When one wants to trade an asset, liquidity is required for the deal to be settled. The more the market is fragmented, the more the order should be split.

Routing orders Smart Order Routers (SOR) are used to make sure that once an order is split, it is split efficiently to minimize its impact over the market while optimizing the fees[12]. One of the critical issues in Europe is the latency between the different venues: London, Paris, Frankfurt, ... This can be extended in Foreign Exchange to the most significant financial hubs: London, New York, Hong Kong.

Tick size The tick size is the minimum increment between two limit orders [12]. Its choice can have a significant impact on market liquidity. Intuitively, as the tick size is lowered, the spread is too since most exchanges have a price-time priority. This means that the buyer who wants to sell quickly as a market maker has the incentive to place his sell order at the best bid offer plus the tick size. This is often referred to as *queue jumping*. So goes for the aggressive market-making buyer who will try to place its buy order at the best ask price minus the tick. Most of the time, the spread has the same size as the tick. However, Lehalle points out that when the tick size is decreased, quoted size decrease too, while the traded volume remains unchanged. A direct consequence of decreasing the tick size is also the fact that liquidity is thinner for each price and it tends to be less stable [12]. Another study [3] also noted that the number of cancellations increases when the tick size is smaller. FX tick sizes tend to be quite large compared to the ones in equity. As an example, one million is often picked by exchanges for NDFs.

Why it matters for a model In this context, a dynamic order book model is required since the positions are smaller and must be refreshed more often. One should keep in mind that the optimal order book should offer much liquidity for each tick, in which case we say it is deep. This means that building the limit order book is very important in order to collect all the information needed to measure the cost of a trade. As the tick size decreases, so do the spread and the potential benefit of a trade [12].

Choosing the tick size Many publications are discussing the choice of the tick size, among which Versoussis' review [18]. According to the latter, one could assess two main criteria which are market quality and market structure depending on the tick size. However, it is important to notice that until today, there is still little research done on how the tick

size affects the execution speed. Vernoussis concludes by stating that as the tick size is reduced, high-frequency traders can implement their strategies with more ease, but that it comes at the cost of higher profits and of the ability of the market to absorb large trades. With the fast development of high-frequency trading, the question of introducing a *resting time* below which transaction would not be regarded as valid has been raised, especially after the 2010 flash crash [18].

Regulation Tick sizes are regulated both in the US and in Europe [12]. The FESE¹ tables in Europe set four different tick sizes [11] depending on the characteristics of the security traded. It is worth noting that these tables are yet not enforced by law [12].

Dark pools and liquidity Dark pools are opaque, so the agents cannot get information on the price from dark pools. They behave however as liquidity wells into which one can execute (large) orders discretely. Lehalle quotes several surveys and draws some conclusions regarding the operation of dark pools:

- Dark pools mostly serve liquid assets;
- Dark pools are of better quality when the market offers high liquidity;
- Dark pools allow to reduce the market impact of deals;
- Liquidity is not the main incentive to use dark pools².

NDF pools are often referred as half lit since information received by market participants is incomplete.

1.3 Fragmentation

As we have just discussed, fragmentation is an integral part of our understanding of volatility regarding market microstructure.

Volume patterns Intraday volume patterns are noticeable and allow for a better understanding of the market behavior and the degree of accuracy of the prices [12]. Here is the intraday volume pattern for different stocks across the globe (figure 1.1 is an extract from Lehalle's book [12]). We can see the same patterns during the day in the FX markets, as business hours for financial institutions are often aligned with the local stock exchange times.

Lehalle also notices that these volumes are impacted by some events such as the publication of some financial news [12].

¹Federation of European Securities Exchanges

²Liquidity available in dark pools is often referred to as *dark liquidity*.

Figure 1.1: Intraday volume patterns across the globe in UTC time [12]

Attracting market makers Some exchanges do not charge market makers in order to attract them [12]. This fare logic is also called maker-taker³. Lehalle states that the satisfaction of market makers depend on the liquidity of the exchange. Liquidity can be assessed according to three main features [12]:

- Volume, which is preferably high;
- Volatility, which is preferably low;
- Bid-ask spread, which is preferably small.

When it comes to designing the market venue, Lehalle [12] notes that although there is little influence on volatility, exchanges try to attract as much volume as possible and to create a narrower bid-ask spread. Indeed, bid-ask spread and market share of the exchanges are linked [12].

Bid-ask spread Bid-ask spread can be represented as a reward for the liquidity provided by market makers [12]. Another important feature is the fact that the bid-ask spread and

³The opposite logic, taker-maker, consists in charging liquidity providers.

volatility move accordingly [12]. One could argue that the round-trip⁴ is often used as a proxy for volatility on larger timescales.

Volatility resistance Last but not least, Lehalle analyses the need for exchanges to mitigate volatility [12]. Indeed, when high-frequency market makers operate on a venue, the quality of the latter improves. As market makers want to lower their investment risk, they will prefer venues with fast trading systems [12].

Impact of high-frequency traders High frequency traders are important agents in the markets since they both provide liquidity and behave as arbitrageurs between different exchanges. While bid-ask spreads tend to be reduced with high-frequency traders, the cost of other participants is unchanged or increased [12]. This is because these traders can easily become the first limit players, so they reduce the bid-ask spread.

Impact on volatility Low intraday volatility indicates equivalent to an efficient market microstructure [12], and intraday volatility is used to measure market risk. In order to measure intraday volatility, *Garman-Klass volatility* is often used [12].

$$\sigma_{GK} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(p_{\Delta_t, \max} - p_{\Delta_t, \min})^2 - (2 \log(2) - 1)(p_{\text{close}} - p_{\text{open}})^2}}{\mu_{\Delta_t}}$$

where μ_{Δ_t} is the average of the price p of the asset over the intraday period Δ_t . It is worth noticing that on intraday scales, market microstructure noise has to be taken into consideration [12, 13]. It is worth also taking into account the correlations between the different assets [12].

Market disruption risk The flash crash on May 6th, 2010 is an example of systemic risk associated with high-frequency trading, although it is not a shred of evidence that systemic risk is increased [12]. This flash-crash has however underlined the lack of circuit breakers and are an example of how algorithms behave in such context.

1.4 What impacts the price

CAPM Framework Following Lehalle's example, we will consider the CAPM⁵ framework in order to model the price of an asset [12]. In this model, the price of an asset is driven by two components, one which is due to the market, and which is also called the *systematic component*, and one which is specific to the asset, the *idiosyncratic component*.

$$p_i(t) = p_{i, \text{systematic}}(t) + p_{i, \text{idiosyncratic}}(t)$$

⁴The instantaneous round trip is precisely the bid-ask spread.

⁵Capital Asset Pricing Model

It follows that the market impact can be broken into two similar components, the systematic and the idiosyncratic market impact.

How to analyze trading impact With intraday analysis, one can quantify the changes to the market price of a given execution [12]. Lehalle comes down to this equation, including duration of the order and PLR⁶.

$$\text{Market Impact} \simeq K \times \text{Duration}^\alpha \times \text{PLR}^\gamma \quad (1.2)$$

where K is a constant.

⁶Participation Liquidity Ratio

Chapter 2

Market Structure

2.1 What is a Non-Deliverable Forward?

A Non-Deliverable Forward (NDF) is a foreign exchange product, often traded alongside spots, designed to provide insurance on the exchange rate of a regulated currency. It has a maturity, which is on average of one month.

2.1.1 A classic FX forward contract

In this section, we will describe a typical forward contract in foreign exchange markets (FX) in order to introduce better what an NDF is.

Figure 2.1: A classic FX forward. In this case, we assume maturity is at time $T=T_5$.

In figure 2.1, a client has bought a bank an option on euro versus pounds. At the beginning of the contract, the client gives the bank one euro plus a fee, in return, the bank guarantees that at maturity T_5 it will pay to pack the client in British pounds at the T_1 rate. One can see that if the client wants to speculate and wants to record its profits in euro, it has to sell the amount given by the bank in the pound versus euro market.

2.1.2 Limitations and NDFs

However, such things are not possible in some emerging markets because of local regulations. Most of the time, emerging countries want to protect themselves from speculation

by separating the on-shore market and the offshore market. This has quickly become an issue for international companies which operate in such countries and still have to report their results in their home country. While they can, and do, convert the local currency to their home currency on the spot market, a new product has been developed so they can have the exchange rate guaranteed, as if they bought a regular option. This product is the Non-Deliverable Forward (NDF).

Figure 2.2: A schematic representation of an NDF contract. In this case, we assume maturity is at time $T=T_5$.

As one can notice in figure 2.2, the bank will not give the customer any Malaysian ringgit. It will, however, give the difference between the spot rate at T_1 and T_5 converted in US dollar. For a company operating a factory in Malaysia and reporting its results at T_5 , it ensures that at the end of the term the bank will pay back the potential losses compared to if the currency was delivered at T_1 . An NDF payoff between two currencies a, b can be formalized as follows.

$$\Pi_{NDF,a,b} = ((P_{ab}(t_M) - P_{ab}(t_0)) \times P_{ba}(t_M)) \quad (2.1)$$

where t_M is the time of maturity, t_0 the time when the contract begins, and P the spot rate. We will study the pricing of NDFs with further details later on.

Hence, most of the NDFs are quoted in US dollar which has a very liquid spot and future market with other major currencies such as euro or yen.

2.1.3 Common NDF currency pairs

Table 2.1 represents common NDF currency pairs, arranged by region and with most liquid tenors¹.

The one the most traded are US dollar versus Indian rupee, US dollar versus Taiwan dollar and US dollar versus Korean Won. Since they are the most liquid, most of the research I have carried was on these currencies.

It is interesting to notice that the currency pairs are clustered geographically, which means that we can identify the same trading activity patterns as for the stocks (figure 1.1).

¹Time to maturity.

Table 2.1: Common NDF currency pairs and tenors [10].

	Currency Pair	Tenors	Country	Name	Time zone
APAC	USD-CNY	1M, 3M	P.R. China	Yuan	Shanghai, UTC+8
	USD-IDR	1M	Indonesia	Rupiah	Jakarta, UTC+7
	USD-INR	1M, EOM	India	Rupee	Mumbai, UTC+5.30
	USD-KRW	1M	South Korea	Won	Seoul, UTC+9
	USD-MYR	1M	Malaysia	Ringgit	Kuala Lumpur, UTC+8
	USD-PHP	1M	Philippines	Peso	Manila, UTC+8
	USD-TWD	1M	Taiwan	Dollar	Taipei, UTC+8
EMEA	USD-RUB	1M	Russia	Ruble	Moscow, UTC+3
LATAM	USD-BRL	1M	Brazil	Real	Sao Paulo, UTC-3
	USD-ARS	1M	Argentina	Peso	Buenos Aires, UTC-3
	USD-CLP	1M	Chile	Peso	Santiago, UTC-3

2.2 Trading Venue

Non-Deliverable Forwards (NDFs) are a foreign exchange product mostly traded with a single venue provider, NEX EBS. There are two pools, in which different regulations apply.

- on-SEF, which complies with the Dodd-Frank Act.
- off-SEF, which does not.

Dodd-Frank Act The Dodd-Frank act [16] was passed in the US Congress and signed into US law on July 21st, 2010 in response to the world financial crisis. The act enforced a series of regulations concerning transparency on some venues, and several regulatory agencies were created or restructured to oversight the implementation of the act. One of these institutions is the US COMMODITY FUTURES TRADING COMMISSION.

In particular, title VI of the act [16] - "Wall Street Transparency And Accountability" - introduces a set of regulations in section two for swap markets. It mainly regulates pre-trade information such as bid and offer prices and regulates the way the execution is processed.

on-SEF SEF stands for *Swap Execution Facility* were created by section 733 of the Dodd-Frank act [16] by amending the previous Commodity Exchange Act which was enacted in 1936 [15]. American counter-parties must abide by this act regardless of the other counter-party. As a result, on SEF venues are mostly active during US business hours. One of the main additional requirements is that market participants must meet minimum margins and have credit lines with the other participants.

off-SEF The off-SEF market is broader and is overall the most active as non-US participants prefer its flexibility.

2.3 A Study of Fragmentation

As discussed in section 1.3, venue fragmentation is an important parameter when we study the market for an asset.

2.3.1 Liquidity pools

An intuitive way to study venue fragmentation is to look at the two different venues: on-SEF and off-SEF. There are three ways to quantify fragmentation:

- Liquidity (see chapter 3)
- Trade activity ratio
- Traded volume
- Tick updates
- Other market activity: news...

We can synthesize all these information into a transition graph 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Schematic market fragmentation for Asian NDFs

As we can see in figure 2.3, there is a transition during the day between off-SEF markets and on-SEF markets. The moment when on-SEF markets are the most active corresponds to US business hours. We can represent fragmentation using entropy as described in section 1.2.

$$H = -\frac{1}{\log N} \sum_{i=1}^N M_i \log M_i \quad (1.1)$$

Equation 1.1 leads to graph 2.4

2.3.2 Another scale of fragmentation

A particular feature of the different markets is that each participant can trade only with agreed counter-parties, depending on the credit lines.

Figure 2.4: Schematic market fragmentation for Asian NDFs - Entropy Profile

This means that on the same liquidity pool, there are in fact as many smaller fragmented markets as there are market participants. It also means there are some arbitrage opportunities between the best price in the market and the price available to some agents. This artificial fragmentation, due to regulatory constraints, can be neglected for tier-1 banks but should be taken into account depending on the client the institution banks with.

Chapter 3

Liquidity

Because of the unusual structure of the NDF market, the study of liquidity is critical towards the understanding of the market microstructure. There is, however, an issue with the concept of liquidity itself: what is liquidity?

An intuitive definition would be to look at liquidity as all the available volume on the visible order book at a given. We will see however that this definition is challenged as it lacks the subtleties needed to get a broader understanding of the order book dynamics. In this section, I will present some results from the same currency pair and explain my reasoning, and how I applied it to derive some prediction signals for the execution algorithm. For obvious confidentiality reasons, I will not disclose which currency pair or the timescale of the study.

However, I would like to point out that I consider median volumes (instead of averages which are more sensitive to extremes) over a period greater than sixty working days.

I chose this specific currency pair because it features very sharp liquidity *moments*, that is epochs in the daily liquidity with distinctive features.

3.1 Aggregated liquidity

In figure 3.1, I have plotted every half an hour the median volume (the axis has been rescaled on the left), bucketed every half hour, on the two main liquidity pools. In this case, it is obvious there is more volume available on SEF than off SEF.

While the profile of aggregated volume bears much information on how liquidity behaves, it only reflects the quantity of the overall liquidity, instead of its quality.

A good visualization is to consider the following paradox.

- Case 1: There is a volume of 500 units at the top of the book on one side, and 50 on the other side. Aggregated liquidity will display 100 at this moment. In this situation, assuming 50 units is quite large in this market, the agent has the choice of the volume to place, but cannot choose the price.
- Case 2: There is a volume of 1 on 50 ticks on either side of the order book, so aggregated liquidity is also 100 in this case. Assuming 1 is a small volume, the agents can choose the price level for their transaction, but not the volume.

Figure 3.1: Rescaled median aggregated liquidity of the currency pair. Source: HSBC

In both cases, the quality of liquidity, which we can define, inspired by Lehalle and Bouchaud's works [6, 12], as the choice of the price and the choice of the volume.

In this specific currency, there is an interesting phenomenon between 8 am and 12 pm UTC, that is that the on SEF venue adds liquidity overall for a short period before it slowly consumes the off SEF liquidity completely.

3.2 Cumulated order book volume imbalance

Cumulated order book imbalance offers a way to quantify the imbalance depending on the level in the order book. Using our new norming method, we have the following equation for rank j , where N is the number of levels in the orderbook. The predictive power of these metrics is known to be quite useful.

$$OBI_{cumulated,j} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^j (V_{ask,i} - V_{bid,i})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (V_{ask,i} + V_{bid,i})}$$

In addition to this signal, we can score how this imbalance jumps between to steps. We prefer to have these jumps as little as possible, so a good measure of the balance could be the following.

$$\beta = 1 - \max_{j \in [1, N-1] \cap \mathbb{N}} \frac{|OBI_{cumulated,j+1} - OBI_{cumulated,j}|}{\max_{l \in [1, N] \cap \mathbb{N}} OBI_{cumulated,k}}$$

Hence, we have $\beta \in [0, 1]$, where 1 is the best score and 0 the worst. Note that for finite N , the number of levels in the order book, we have $\max_{j \in [1, N] \cap \mathbb{N}} OBI_{cumulated,j} = 1$.

It is apparent in figure 3.2 that the balance β remains quite high, even with low liquidity. However, every product has some specificities, and β seems to bring new information towards understanding the price formation process and the evolution of liquidity.

Figure 3.2: Daily median order book imbalance of the currency pair. Source: HSBC

3.2.1 Liquidity entropy

The definition of entropy in Physics inspired us.

$$H_{side}(t) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{V_{side,i}}{V_{side,total}} \log \left(\frac{V_{side,i}}{V_{side,total}} \right), V_{side,total} = \sum_{i=1}^N V_{side,i}$$

where $V_{side,i}$ is the volume in the order book on one side at depth i out of N .

Figure 3.3: Median liquidity entropy of the currency pair. Source: HSBC

Figure 3.3 is very instructive, as we discover that at some moments during the day there are some moments of null entropy¹. This means that either there is no volume, or that all the volume is stacked at the top of the order book. These moments of null entropy can be used to define moments with poor liquidity. A better interpretation of the null case will be provided with the position score δ described later on.

The main problem with this metric is that it is unbounded and lacks precision, that is if there is a lot of liquidity at top of book level, entropy will still be null while the market is liquid. We have to develop other metrics to capture such situations.

3.2.2 Liquidity compactness

Our measure of liquidity compactness draws its inspiration from the Atomic Packing Factor (APF) in crystallography. The idea is to draw a virtual box around the volumes at the available ticks and to see how much the actual volume in the order book fills it, as seen in figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: A schematic representation of liquidity compactness. The gray dotted boxes correspond to the maximum volume available.

We can write liquidity compactness as follows.

$$\rho_{side}(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N V_{side,i}}{N \times \max_{i \in [1,N] \cap \mathbb{N}} V_{side,i}}$$

where $V_{side,i}$ is the volume in the order book on one side at depth i out of N . Compactness measures how different the volume sizes are on the ticks. A very compact order book might be likely to increase the market impact of an order compared to a non-compact one.

In practice, liquidity compactness and entropy are significantly correlated. However, the main downside of liquidity is that it is not bounded, while compactness is, which makes the latter an excellent prediction and scoring signal for algorithms.

Another issue is that liquidity compactness lacks directionality, which is the reason why we developed the position score.

¹Instead of referring to zero entropy, which is impossible in Physics, null entropy is preferred.

3.3 Position score

One of the most critical information is, however, to know where the pressure lies on each side: whether is it on top of the book or deeper. I have introduced the position score δ as a signal which models how the order book looks at a given time t .

$$\delta_{side}(t) = -\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (2i - N) \times V_{side,i}(t)}{2N \sum_{i=1}^N V_{side,i}(t)}$$

where $V_{side,i}$ is the volume in the order book on one side at depth i out of N . δ is a score, $\delta \in [-0.5, 0.5]$, which returns the location where there is the more volume. If ρ is close to 1, δ is close to $\frac{N}{2}$. In a case of an execution strategy, taking the rounded value of $\delta_{side,adjusted}(t)$ gives the level in the order book with the most liquidity.

Figure 3.5: Median liquidity position score for the currency pair. Source: HSBC

The interpretation of the position score is the following. A score close to 0.5 means most of the volume is at the top of the book. A score around 0 can either mean the score is in the middle of the book if there is an odd number of price levels, or that it is evenly spread across all ticks. This is why δ is better interpreted in association with ρ for the null case. When the position score is close to -0.5 , it means that most of the volumes tend to be deeper in the order book.

It appears very clearly that in moments of low liquidity, especially when entropy is equal to 0 (see Figure 3.3) there is actually volume in the order book, but it is wholly located at the top of the book, as the economic agents tend to reposition their order to maximize its chances to be filled.

The round-trip cost is a direct measure of liquidity for different price levels. However, in situations where the information in the order book is partially hidden², such metrics give an intuition of the nature of liquidity and of the costs implied.

²This is the case for NDFs, where many orders are placed as 3iceberg³, that is the volume is partially disclosed to the other market participants.

Chapter 4

Volatility

There are several ways to define volatility which we are going to explore in this part, as they each have their advantages, especially towards identifying remarkable features, called stylized facts [13, 14]. The two different measures of volatility we are going to study are the following.

- Standard deviation of returns
- Log-returns

These two volatility proxies will help us understand the market.

4.1 Standard deviation of returns

The standard deviation of returns is one of the most commonly used measures of volatility [14]. Indeed, it is always positive and corresponds to an inherent statistical property of the distribution of the results. However, it is not always the most appropriate as the return data must be bucketed in order to derive statistical analysis.

We already know that the shape of a financial distribution may change significantly as we select short or long time periods. The other issue is that bucketing data requires to have an even flow of information. Indeed, in an illiquid market like the NDFs, it would not make sense to create such buckets as, during a specific moment of the day, there are more than a hundred movements per second, while during other moments, there are at most ten movements per hour.

This is the main reason why this measure of volatility was discarded for our quantitative study of NDFs.

4.2 Log-returns

Log-returns for a financial signal $s(t)$ are defined as follows.

$$r(t_k) = \log \left(\frac{s(t_k)}{s(t_{k-1})} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

Log-returns are also widely used in the industry. As they can be computed at every tick, it is much easier to use them on markets which have very different liquidity - and volatility - regimes, like the NDF market. We can plot the daily log-returns at fixing time for four of the NDF assets we study in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Log-returns for the Four NDF Assets

Note that we had to clean the data from errors. Due to the extreme sensitivity of this measure, the errors in our data set create extreme points. Most of these errors are due to historical events, including diplomatic and economic events in the Asia-Pacific region between 2015 and 2018.

The study of log-return will also allow us, later on, to derive some models for the NDFs.

Part II

Risk Management

Chapter 5

Pricing a NDF

5.1 Payoff

5.1.1 Deriving a pricing equation

We first can recall equation 5.2 which describes the payoff of an NDF.

$$\Pi_{NDF,a,b} = ((P_{ab}(t_M) - P_{ab}(t_0)) \times P_{ba}(t_M)) \quad (5.2)$$

where t_M is the time of maturity, t_0 the time when the contract begins, and P the spot rate.

We should, however, discuss one of the subtleties of the FX market, that is since P is the spot rate, a more consistent way to write equation 5.2 would be the following.

$$\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t_0 - 2) = ((P_{ab}(t_M) - P_{ab}(t_0)) \times P_{ba}(t_M)) \quad (5.1)$$

where we consider $(t_i)_{i \in \mathbb{Z}}$ a time series of days. Indeed, by convention, the spot rate at date $t_0 - 2$ is the exchange rate for a delivery at date t_0 . In order to simplify our notations, and since the spot rate is the most common reference in the FX market, we will ignore this subtlety and carry on with equation 5.2.

It is also worth noticing that theoretically, we should have the following.

$$P_{ab}(t) = \frac{1}{P_{ba}(t)}, \quad \forall t$$

In practice, this is wrong for several reasons:

- The market displays at a given time two prices, bid and ask, and the spread is not zero.
- The larger the amounts, the larger the spread for a given volume widens, and the less this approximation is true.
- Some NDFs are quite illiquid, which means that the spread can even be infinite.

We will, however, use this approximation for the following calculations as we will focus on

the smallest NDF amount¹ which is quite liquid for most currency pairs and which has a spread negligible compared to the price of the asset. This gives us the following payoff for the receiver NDF.

$$\Pi_{NDF,a,b} = \left(1 - \frac{P_{ab}(t_0)}{P_{ab}(t_M)} \right) \quad (5.2)$$

As we will now try to price the NDF, we obtain the following pricing at t_0 .

$$NDF_{a,b}(t_0) = \mathbf{E} \left[1 - \frac{P_{ab}(t_0)}{P_{ab}(t_M)} \right] \quad (5.3)$$

5.1.2 Pricing

An NDF is somehow to foreign exchange markets what a Forward Rate Agreement is to fixed income. We can quickly notice there is a parallel to be drawn with a bond [7]. We will use the classic bond price formula, which would become the following.

$$P_{ab}(t) = P_{ab}(0)e^{\int_0^t r(u)du} \quad (5.4)$$

However, since the convention in foreign exchange is to price the spot, that is a two day forward, it comes that the NDF is more analogous to a fixed income forward contract rather than to an FRA. The previous $P_{ab}(T) = P_{ab}(t, T)$ would define the price at time t in currency b of one unit of currency a for delivery at time time, analogously to a zero-coupon bond. The main difference is in the way the NDF is discounted. Inspired by equation 5.3, we can derive the receiver NDF pricing formula (equation 5.5).

$$NDF_{a,b}(t, t_0, t_M) = D_{investor,b}(t, t_M) \mathbf{E}_t \left[1 - \frac{P_{ab}(t, t_0)}{P_{ab}(t, t_M)} \right] \quad (5.5)$$

The discounting parameter $D_{investor,b}(t, M)$ is written in currency b and is driven by another interest rate than the one defined in equation 5.4. Thus, we can now consider $r(u)$ as the implied spot rate between currencies a and b , and we will suggest several methods to model it.

Taking into consideration equation 5.4, equation 5.5 becomes the following theorem 5.1.

Theorem 5.1. *The price of a receiver NDF at time t , with maturity t_M and spot rate t_0 can be written as follows.*

$$NDF_{a,b}(t, t_0, t_M) = D(t, t_M) \mathbf{E}_t \left[1 - e^{-\int_{t_0}^{t_M} r(u)du} \right] \quad (5.5)$$

where $r(\cdot)$ is the implied spot rate between a and b and $D(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the discount factor for the investor in currency b of the form

$$D(t, t_M) = D(t, t) e^{\int_t^{t_M} r_{investor}(u)du}$$

where $r_{investor}(\cdot)$ is the interest rate for the investor in currency b .

¹One million units.

Corollary 5.1. *Using the same notations as in theorem 5.1, the price of a payer NDF at time t , with maturity t_M and spot rate t_0 can be written as follows.*

$$NDF_{a,b}(t, t_0, t_M) = D(t, t_M) \mathbf{E}_t \left[e^{-\int_{t_0}^{t_M} r(u) du} - 1 \right] \quad (5.6)$$

5.1.3 Another way to derive the price of an NDF

I will present an alternative way to derive the price of an NDF. One can consider a foreign exchange bond. There are now several rates we can consider. We suppose an investor, whose local currency is b , wants to invest in a foreign exchange bond in currency a . The investor will reason as follows to price the forward to protect his investment. We can write the forward as follows.

$$F(t, t_0, t_M) = Spot(t) \frac{Bond_{invest,a}(t_M - t_0)}{Bond_{borrow,b}(t_M - t_0)}$$

This equation can then be rewritten in a other way.

- r_{borrow} which is the borrowing rate for the investor.
- r_{invest} which is the investment rate for the investor.

$$F(t, t_0, t_M) = Spot(t) \frac{1 - r_{borrow} \times (t_M - t_0)}{1 - r_{invest} \times (t_M - t_0)}$$

Making the approximation that the rates are very small, we can deduce by first order Taylor series the following.

$$F(t, t_0, t_M) \sim Spot(t)(r_{borrow} - r_{invest}) \times (t_M - t_0)$$

As we discount in currency b (assuming here the rates are constant) and go to the expectation, we recover equation 5.5.

5.1.4 A linear rate for term structure

Continuing our analogy with fixed income, we can also derive an equivalent to LIBOR rate, in an attempt to recover a term structure curve $\mathcal{C}_{ab}(t, T)$. We assume the following.

$$P_{ab}(t, T)(1 + (T - t) \times \mathcal{C}_{ab}(t, T)) = 1$$

Which leads to equation 5.7.

$$\mathcal{C}_{ab}(t, T) = \frac{1 - P_{ab}(t, T)}{(T - t)P_{ab}(t, T)} \quad (5.7)$$

Note that with this definition, we can deduce equation 5.8, which is now another way to write the receiver NDF price. K is the fixed amount received.

$$\begin{aligned} NDF_{a,b}(t, t_0, t_M) &= \mathbf{E}_t [(t_M - t_0)D_{investor,b}(t, t_M) \times K - D_{investor,b}(t, t_M) \times \mathcal{C}_{ab}(t_0, t_M)] \\ &= \mathbf{E}_t [D_{investor,b}(t, t_M) ((t_M - t_0) \times K - \mathcal{C}_{ab}(t_0, t_M))] \end{aligned}$$

$$NDF_{a,b}(t, t_0, t_M) = D_{investor,b}(t, t_M) \mathbf{E}_t [(t_M - t_0) \times K - \mathcal{C}_{ab}(t_0, t_M)] \quad (5.8)$$

5.2 Modeling the implied spot rate

Recall equation 5.4 where we defined the implied spot rate. There are several models which can be used. The main idea in this section is to provide the mathematical framework in order to try to use volatility product results for NDFs.

5.2.1 Vasicek model

A good first choice is to use the Vasicek model [17], as it is linear and can be solved explicitly. The corresponding Gaussian (stochastic differential equation) SDE is the following.

$$dr(u) = k(\theta - r(u))du + \sigma dW(u) \quad (5.9)$$

$W(u)$ is the standard Brownian motion.

The Vasicek model is also mean-reverting [7], which is an interesting property we will use when we calibrate the model. It can be applied over the NDFs since most of the developing economies corresponding to the assets we study have been relatively stable in the past years with quite constant growth rates.

We start with equation 5.9.

$$\begin{aligned} dr(u) &= k(\theta - r(u))du + \sigma dW(u) \\ d(e^{ku}r(u)) &= ke^{ku}r(u)du + e^{ku}dr(u) \\ &= ke^{ku}r(u)du + e^{ku}(k(\theta - r(u))du + \sigma dW(u)) \\ &= e^{ku}(k\theta du + \sigma dW(u)) \end{aligned}$$

We can now integrate on both sides.

$$\begin{aligned} e^{ku}r(u) - e^{ks}r(s) &= \int_s^u ke^{kx}\theta dx + \int_s^u e^{kx}\sigma dW(x) \\ r(u) &= r(s)e^{-k(u-s)} + \theta(1 - e^{-k(u-s)}) + \int_s^u e^{-k(u-x)}\sigma dW(x) \end{aligned}$$

As we want to calibrate a Vasicek model, later on, we will compute the conditional expectation $\mathbf{E}(\cdot)$ and the variance $\mathbf{Var}(\cdot)$ to deduce the values of k, θ, σ .

The equation comes relatively quickly, as written in equation 5.10.

$$\mathbf{E}[r(t)|r(s)] = r(s)e^{-k(t-s)} + \theta(1 - e^{-k(t-s)}) \quad (5.10)$$

In order to compute the conditional variance, we will use Ito's isometry.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Var}[r(t)|r(s)] &= \mathbf{Var} \left[\int_s^t e^{-k(t-x)} \sigma dW(x) \right] \\ &= \int_s^t e^{-2k(t-u)} \sigma^2 du \\ \mathbf{Var}[r(t)|r(s)] &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-2k(t-s)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5.11)$$

The Vasicek model allows however for negative rates. Since we are looking at an implied spot rate, this assumption is not very realistic.

5.2.2 CIR model

The Cox Ingersoll Ross [9] model implies positive interest rates, but a non-central chi-squared distribution characterizes the instantaneous rate [7]. The corresponding Gaussian SDE is the following.

$$dr(u) = k(\theta - r(u))du + \sigma\sqrt{r(u)}dW(u) \quad (5.12)$$

$W(u)$ is the standard Brownian motion and where $\sigma^2 < 2k\theta$. We have the following expectations and variance for the CIR model [7].

$$\mathbf{E}[r(t)|r(s)] = r(s)e^{-k(t-s)} + \theta(1 - e^{-k(t-s)}) \quad (5.13)$$

$$\mathbf{Var}[r(t)|r(s)] = \theta \frac{\sigma^2}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-k(t-s)} \right)^2 + r(s) \frac{\sigma^2}{k} \left(e^{-k(t-s)} - e^{-2k(t-s)} \right) \quad (5.14)$$

Chapter 6

Model fitting and simulation

In order to check the assumptions we formulated in chapter 5, we will first derive a way from our data to calibrate a model and then do a Monte-Carlo simulation.

6.1 Calibration methodology

Calibration consists of choosing based on our data sample the parameters of our models. Since we have chosen both the Vasicek and the CIR model, calibration will be done separately.

6.1.1 Calibration of the Vasicek model

Recall the expression 5.9 describing the Vasicek model.

$$dr(u) = k(\theta - r(u))du + \sigma dW(u) \quad (5.9)$$

$W(u)$ is the standard Brownian motion. We can calibrate the parameters of the model, which are θ , σ and k , using the expectation and the variance.

$$\mathbf{E}[r(t)|r(s)] = r(s)e^{-k(t-s)} + \theta(1 - e^{-k(t-s)}) \quad (5.10)$$

$$\mathbf{Var}[r(t)|r(s)] = \frac{\sigma^2}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-2k(t-s)}\right) \quad (5.11)$$

Notice that we only have two equations for three variables, so we must make some additional assumptions. Here are the assumptions I will make and their justification.

1. The electronic NDFs market is very recent, but I will assume that the expectation at $t \rightarrow \infty$ corresponds to the mean value observed since the market opened.
2. The market stabilized itself during the past two years, as the developing economies associated with the NDFs currency pairs have since sustained a stable rhythm of growth.

According to assumption 1, we can derive from 5.10 the following.

$$\begin{aligned}\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{E}[r(t)|r(0)] &= \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(0)] \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left[r(0)e^{-kt} + \theta(1 - e^{-kt}) \right] &= \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(0)] \\ \theta &= \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(0)]\end{aligned}$$

According to assumption 2, we may now derive k from 5.10. As the underlying economies had stable growth in the past two years, it follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] &= r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})e^{-k\Delta_2 \text{ years}} + \theta(1 - e^{-k\Delta_2 \text{ years}}) \\ \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] - \theta &= (r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) - \theta)e^{-k\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \\ -k\Delta_2 \text{ years} &= \ln \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] - \theta}{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) - \theta} \right) \\ k &= \frac{1}{\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \ln \left(\frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) - \theta}{\mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] - \theta} \right)\end{aligned}$$

Still according to our second assumption, we can now derive σ from 5.11.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] &= \frac{\sigma_{Vasicek}^2}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-2k\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \right) \\ \sigma_{Vasicek} &= \sqrt{\frac{2k \mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})]}{1 - e^{-2k\Delta_2 \text{ years}}}}\end{aligned}$$

6.1.2 Calibration of the CIR model

Recall the expression 5.12 describing the CIR model.

$$dr(u) = k(\theta - r(u))du + \sigma\sqrt{r(u)}dW(u) \quad (5.12)$$

$W(u)$ is the standard Brownian motion and where $\sigma^2 < 2k\theta$.

We can calibrate the parameters of the model, which are θ , σ and k , using the same methodology as the one we used previously for the Vasicek model. We immediately notice that the expectations 5.10 and 5.13 are identical.

$$\mathbf{E}[r(t)|r(s)] = r(s)e^{-k(t-s)} + \theta(1 - e^{-k(t-s)}) \quad (5.13)$$

This means that if we apply the same assumptions as previously, we obtain the same θ and k .

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &= \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(0)] \\ k &= \frac{1}{\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \ln \left(\frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) - \theta}{\mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] - \theta} \right)\end{aligned}$$

However, the variance for CIR is different.

$$\mathbf{Var}[r(t)|r(s)] = \theta \frac{\sigma^2}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-k(t-s)}\right)^2 + r(s) \frac{\sigma^2}{k} \left(e^{-k(t-s)} - e^{-2k(t-s)}\right) \quad (5.14)$$

Using assumptions 1 and 2, we obtain the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_{2 \text{ years}})] &= \theta \frac{\sigma^2}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-k\Delta_{2 \text{ years}}}\right)^2 \\ &\quad + r(t_{now} - \Delta_{2 \text{ years}}) \frac{\sigma^2}{k} \left(e^{-k\Delta_{2 \text{ years}}} - e^{-2k\Delta_{2 \text{ years}}}\right) \\ \mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta)] &= \sigma^2 \left(\frac{\theta}{2k} \left(1 - e^{-k\Delta}\right)^2 + \frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta)}{k} \left(e^{-k\Delta} - e^{-2k\Delta}\right) \right) \\ \sigma &= \sqrt{\frac{k \mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta)]}{\frac{\theta}{2} \left(1 - e^{-k\Delta}\right)^2 + r(t_{now} - \Delta) \left(e^{-k\Delta} - e^{-2k\Delta}\right)}} \end{aligned}$$

6.2 Calibration results

6.2.1 Mathematical considerations

The main idea is to calibrate the implicit spot rate for NDFs (which does not exist). Note that the implicit spot rate for NDFs has nothing to do with the actual spot rate of the currency the NDFs is built upon. Recall the implicit spot rate R_t from 5.4.

$$R_t = \int_0^t r(u) du$$

We can recall the observed price of an NDF from 5.2

$$\Pi_{NDF,a,b} = \left(1 - \frac{P_{ab}(t_0)}{P_{ab}(t_M)}\right) \quad (5.2)$$

where the implicit price can we write as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} P_{ab}(t) &= P_{ab}(0) e^{\int_0^t r(u) du} \\ &= P_{ab}(0) e^{R_t} \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

Moreover, we will try to derive from it the implicit spot rate.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+1)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)} &= \frac{1 - \frac{P_{ab}(0)}{P_{ab}(t+1)}}{1 - \frac{P_{ab}(0)}{P_{ab}(t)}} \\
\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+1)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)} &= \frac{P_{ab}(t)}{P_{ab}(t+1)} \frac{P_{ab}(0) - P_{ab}(t+1)}{P_{ab}(0) - P_{ab}(t)} \\
\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+1)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right) &= \ln\left(\frac{P_{ab}(t)}{P_{ab}(t+1)}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{P_{ab}(0) - P_{ab}(t+1)}{P_{ab}(0) - P_{ab}(t)}\right) \\
&= \ln\left(\frac{P_{ab}(0)e^{R_t}}{P_{ab}(0)e^{R_{t+1}}}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{P_{ab}(0) - P_{ab}(0)e^{R_{t+1}}}{P_{ab}(0) - P_{ab}(0)e^{R_t}}\right) \\
&= \ln\left(\frac{e^{R_t}}{e^{R_{t+1}}}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{1 - e^{R_{t+1}}}{1 - e^{R_t}}\right) \\
&\sim \ln\left(\frac{e^{R_t}}{e^{R_{t+1}}}\right) \\
&\sim R_t - R_{t+1}
\end{aligned}$$

So in conclusion, we have the following equation which approximates the increments of the implied spot rate by the opposite of the log-returns.

$$R_{t+1} = R_t - \ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+1)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right) \quad (6.1)$$

6.2.2 Log-returns approximation

We will now try to link 6.1 with the expectation of the log-returns by using Fubini's theorem.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{E}[R_{t+\delta_t}] &= \mathbf{E}[R_t] - \mathbf{E}\left[\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+\delta_t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right)\right] \\
\mathbf{E}[R_{t+\delta_t} - R_t] &= -\mathbf{E}\left[\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+\delta_t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right)\right] \\
\mathbf{E}\left[\int_t^{t+\delta_t} r(u)du\right] &= -\mathbf{E}\left[\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+\delta_t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right)\right] \\
\int_t^{t+\delta_t} \mathbf{E}[r(u)] du &= -\mathbf{E}\left[\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+\delta_t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right)\right] \\
\int_t^{t+\delta_t} \mathbf{E}[r(u)] du &\sim (t + \delta_t - t)\mathbf{E}[r(t)] \\
\mathbf{E}[r(t)] &\sim -\mathbf{E}\left[\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+\delta_t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right)\right]
\end{aligned}$$

We can do similar computations for the variance, which gives us the following.

$$\mathbf{Var}[r(t)] \sim \mathbf{Var}\left[\ln\left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t+\delta_t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}\right)\right]$$

6.2.3 Statistical results

We are now able to derive from the observed log-returns an approximation of the expectation and variance of the implied NDF spot rate, and we can proceed to the calibration. Using R, we can compute the expectation and the variance of the log-returns of our sample.

Table 6.1: Log-returns Statistical Data

	Asset A (%)	Asset B (%)	Asset C (%)	Asset D (%)
Mean (all time)	1.152 10e-2	1.258 10e-2	1.442 10e-2	1.430 10e-2
Mean (2 years)	-1.161 10e-2	-1.377 10e-2	2.118 10e-2	2.062 10e-2
Standard deviation (2 years)	5.933 10e-1	2.730 10e-1	2.786 10e-1	2.785 10e-1

Vasicek calibration

Recall the results in the previous section for the Vasicek model.

$$\theta = \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(0)]$$

$$k = \frac{1}{\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \ln \left(\frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) - \theta}{\mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] - \theta} \right)$$

$$\sigma_{Vasicek} = \sqrt{\frac{2k \mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})]}{1 - e^{-2k\Delta_2 \text{ years}}}}$$

We can now apply the log-returns approximation we developed previously.

$$\theta = -\mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(0)} \right) \right]$$

$$k = \frac{1}{\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \ln \left(\frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) + \mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(0)} \right) \right]}{\mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(0)} \right) \right] - \mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t - \Delta_2 \text{ years})} \right) \right]} \right)$$

$$\sigma_{Vasicek} = \sqrt{\frac{2k \mathbf{Var} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t - \Delta_2 \text{ years})} \right) \right]}{1 - e^{-2k\Delta_2 \text{ years}}}}$$

We can derive the values from table 6.1.

Table 6.2: Vasicek Calibrated Parameters

	Asset A	Asset B	Asset C	Asset D
$r(0)$	1.463 10e-4	3.065 10e-3	9.166 10e-4	9.158 10e-4
$r(t - \Delta_2 \text{ years})$	5.425 10e-3	3.198 10e-3	1.509 10e-3	3.233 10e-4
θ	-1.152 10e-4	-1.258 10e-4	-1.442 10e-4	-1.430 10e-4
k	6.502 10e-5	2.236 10e-3	1.956 10e-4	8.671 10e-4
$\sigma_{Vasicek}$	4.755 10e-4	4.185 10e-3	3.315 10e-3	3.609 10e-3

CIR calibration

Recall the results in the previous section for the CIR model.

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &= \mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(0)] \\ k &= \frac{1}{\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \ln \left(\frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) - \theta}{\mathbf{E}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years})] - \theta} \right) \\ \sigma_{CIR} &= \sqrt{\frac{k \mathbf{Var}[r(t_{now})|r(t_{now} - \Delta)]}{\frac{\theta}{2}(1 - e^{-k\Delta})^2 + r(t_{now} - \Delta)(e^{-k\Delta} - e^{-2k\Delta})}}\end{aligned}$$

We can now apply the log-returns approximation we developed previously.

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &= -\mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(0)} \right) \right] \\ k &= \frac{1}{\Delta_2 \text{ years}} \ln \left(\frac{r(t_{now} - \Delta_2 \text{ years}) + \mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(0)} \right) \right]}{\mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(0)} \right) \right] - \mathbf{E} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t - \Delta_2 \text{ years})} \right) \right]} \right) \\ \sigma_{CIR} &= \sqrt{\frac{k \mathbf{Var} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t)}{\Pi_{NDF,a,b}(t - \Delta_2 \text{ years})} \right) \right]}{\frac{\theta}{2}(1 - e^{-k\Delta_2 \text{ years}})^2 + r(t - \Delta_2 \text{ years})(e^{-k\Delta_2 \text{ years}} - e^{-2k\Delta_2 \text{ years}})}}\end{aligned}$$

We can derive the values from table 6.1. Only the variance differs from the Vasicek case (table 6.2).

Table 6.3: CIR Calibrated Parameters

	Asset A	Asset B	Asset C	Asset D
σ_{CIR}	2.910 10e-4	2.598 10e-4	2.029 10e-4	2.214 10e-4

Note that the values of *theta* and *k* do not change compared to the Vasicek calibration. We also notice that for every asset, $\sigma_{CIR}^2 < |2k\theta|$.

6.3 Monte-Carlo simulation

In order to simulate various paths, we code the Vasicek and the CIR models in C++. This allows for improved speed and performance. Plots are done in Python 3.6, and statistical calibration in R.

6.3.1 Models

Models are simulated in C++ for maximum efficiency. We take advantage of the random number generation pre-built in the `random` library to create the Brownian motion increments.

Given a stochastic differential equation

$$dx = f(x)dx + g(x)dW$$

where f and g are appropriately defined functions, we can simulate the following. This method is called the Euler approximation [19].

$$x[k+1] = f(x[k]) * \text{delta} + g(x[k]) * X$$

where X is a sample from the random normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0,1)$, generated using the `random` package in C++.

Vasicek Model

We simulate the Vasicek model on 3625 days (ten years).

Figure 6.1: Sample Paths obtained by Vasicek Simulation

CIR Model

We immediately notice the calibration of the CIR model led to smaller variations in amplitude. We expect to see an impact on our simulations. We simulate the model on 2192 days (six years).

Figure 6.2: Sample Paths obtained by CIR Simulation

(a) Sample Path - Asset A

(b) Sample Path - Asset B

(c) Sample Path - Asset C

(d) Sample Path - Asset D

6.3.2 Implicit NDF Spot Rate

Recall our definition of the implicit NDF spot rate R_t .

$$R_t = \int_0^t r(u) du$$

With small enough time steps δ_i , we can do the following approximation.

$$\int_0^t r(u) du \sim \sum_{i=0}^N r_k \delta_i$$

$$R_t \sim \sum_{i=0}^N r_k \delta_i$$

In our case, the day is the smallest possible unit, so we can build as previously the different implicit spot rates paths. In figure 6.3, we represent 20 of such simulated paths for each model.

Due to the quite small values of the parameters of the Vasicek model (table 6.2) and espe-

Figure 6.3: Implicit NDF Spot Rates Paths for Asset A

cially of the CIR model (table 6.3), we observe quite few jitteriness of the processes. This is also due to the fact we have chosen currency pairs corresponding to economies displaying very stable growth patterns over the past three years.

Term structure of implicit NDF spot rate

Recall now how we built the fictional NDF "spot" price.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{ab}(t) &= P_{ab}(0, t) = P_{ab}(0) e^{\int_0^t r(u) du} \\
 &= P_{ab}(0) e^{R_T} \\
 &\sim P_{ab}(0) e^{\sum_{i=0}^N r_k \delta_i}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

The construction of such a spot price eventually leads to a fictional term curve, based on equation 5.7.

$$\mathcal{C}_{ab}(t, T) = \frac{1 - P_{ab}(t, T)}{(T - t)P_{ab}(t, T)} \tag{5.7}$$

We can now plot such term structure curves for sample paths. Figure 6.4 represents such curves for sample paths generated by Vasicek simulation, figure 6.5 represents such curves for sample paths generated by CIR simulation.

A standard interpretation for such curves is that a downward pointing curve represents a currency the investors expect to be depreciated while an upward pointing curve represents a currency expected to gain appreciation. While there is no such curve for NDFs, we can compare to the forward curves for on-shore investors.

Figure 6.4: Implied Term Curve for Sample Paths - Vasicek Simulation

(a) Sample Path Implied Term Curve- Asset A (b) Sample Path Implied Term Curve - Asset D

Figure 6.5: Implied Term Curve for Sample Paths - CIR Simulation

(a) Sample Path Implied Term Curve- Asset A (b) Sample Path Implied Term Curve - Asset D

As we use Monte-Carlo simulations, we obtain smoother and statistically more accurate paths. Figure 6.6 is an example of how the real term curves look like for assets A, B and D. Note that the scale is not linear.

Figure 6.6: Observed Term Structure for Assets A, B and C. Source: Reuters

The accuracy of these simulations could be improved by using other models, such as Black-Karasinski (extended exponential Vasicek) or CIR++. Other methods to approximate integrals such as the Milstein scheme [19] could also be used.

Chapter 7

Modeling volatility

Generally speaking, asset returns are not independent but are serially correlated [14]. This is also true for the returns of the NDFs.

There is a dependence in the financial time series, which is not of a linear nature, that we can model. Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) [5, 14] models can be used to capture such features.

7.1 Modeling volatility

7.1.1 Volatility proxy

One of the most common measures of volatility is the log-returns of the asset (see section 4). Recall the equation 4.1.

$$r(t_k) = \log \left(\frac{s(t_k)}{s(t_{k-1})} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

These returns are represented in figure 4.1. We can see there is at some moments some clustering and some persistence. One of the most convenient ways to model persistence, over an ARMA process as an example, is to use a GARCH model.

Due to the high sensitivity of such volatility measure, data has been cleaned to prevent extreme - and unrealistic - jumps. These jumps are most of the time due to errors in the recording. In our case, about five rows out of 1054 were removed for each asset.

7.1.2 GARCH model

Let $(X_t)_{t \in \mathbb{Z}}$ be a GARCH(p,q) process [5]. We have the following.

$$X_t = \sigma_t Z_t \quad (7.1)$$

$$\sigma_t^2 = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i X_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^q \beta_j \sigma_{t-j}^2 \quad (7.2)$$

where $Z \sim \text{SWN}(0, 1)$, $\alpha_0 > 0$, $\alpha_i \geq 0, \forall i \in [1, p] \cap \mathbb{Z}$ and $\beta_i \geq 0, \forall i \in [1, q] \cap \mathbb{Z}$.

In equation 7.2, the left-hand side sum represents volatility clustering and the right-hand side sum represents volatility persistence.

We know from the lecture notes that usually, a GARCH(1,1) model is a good fit for log-returns data. In our case, X_t will be the log returns in equations 7.1 and 7.2.

7.2 GARCH fitting and results

In our case, we fit the GARCH(1,1) model with a constant conditional mean. Fitting is done using `QRM` and `rugarch` packages in R [14].

7.2.1 Parameters of the model

In our case, we have fitted the model with innovations following a normal random variable. We present in table 7.1 the results of the fitting for each asset. In our case, α_0 is noted ω , and μ is the conditional mean.

The main reason why we chose to use the normal random variable is that it tends to be a good fit for daily returns, especially on foreign exchange markets. Student t-distribution is preferred for stock values or on shorter timescales.

Table 7.1: Fitted Parameters of GARCH(1,1)

	Estimate	Std. Error	p-value		Estimate	Std. Error	p-value
μ_A	0.02	0.02	0.48	μ_B	0.01	0.01	0.32
ω_A	0.00	0.00	0.96	ω_B	0.00	0.00	0.99
$\alpha_{A,1}$	3.54	14.92	0.81	$\alpha_{B,1}$	0.69	0.26	0.08
$\beta_{A,1}$	95.49	15.23	0.00	$\beta_{B,1}$	98.76	1.63	0.00
	Estimate	Std. Error	p-value		Estimate	Std. Error	p-value
μ_C	0.02	0.02	0.19	μ_D	0.01	0.01	0.24
ω_C	0.00	0.00	0.99	ω_D	0.00	0.00	0.99
$\alpha_{C,1}$	0.05	1.86	0.98	$\alpha_{D,1}$	1.00	31.68	0.97
$\beta_{C,1}$	99.58	0.87	0.00	$\beta_{D,1}$	98.61	33.41	0.01

We can notice that in all cases, the conditional mean μ is very close to zero. This is an expected result as there is little drift for log-returns, as one can see in figure 4.1.

We can plot the residuals of the GARCH(1,1) model for some of the assets (figure 7.1). However, we need to quantify the quality of the residuals to determine the quality of the fit.

(a) Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset A (b) Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset D

Figure 7.1: Adjusted GARCH Residuals

7.2.2 Assessment

Since we chose to build a model with normal innovations, we will try to assess how close to normal the distribution of the residuals is. We first plot some histograms to have an overview on figure 7.2, with the normal kernel density distribution associated.

(a) Histogram of Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset B (b) Histogram of Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset C

Figure 7.2: Histogram of Adjusted GARCH Residuals

We can notice the distribution of the tails seems to be appropriate. If the tails were thicker compared to the normal distribution, we would have tried to compare it with a Student t-distribution.

There are two ways to assess precisely how close to the normal distributions these residuals

are:

- Plotting the Empirical CDF of the residuals against a fitted normal distribution CDF, as seen on figure 7.3.
- Creating the QQ-plots of the residuals, as seen in figure 7.4.

(a) Adjusted GARCH Residuals ECDF - Asset A (b) Adjusted GARCH Residuals ECDF - Asset C

Figure 7.3: Adjusted GARCH Residuals ECDF

Generally speaking, QQ-plots are more precise at assessing the quality of a fit to a distribution. Indeed, it is easier to see the difference in tail values.

We can see on figure 7.4 that the fit is quite good. It means the assumption we took to use normal distributions were right.

(a) QQ-Plot of Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset A (b) QQ-Plot of Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset B

(c) QQ-Plot of Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset C (d) QQ-Plot of Adjusted GARCH Residuals - Asset D

Figure 7.4: QQ-Plot of Adjusted GARCH Residuals

7.2.3 Autocorrelation function

We can also plot the ACF of the residuals to check that they satisfy some of the assumptions of the GARCH model.

Recall the ACF of a signal $s(t_k)$

$$\rho(k, l) := \text{Cor}[s(t_k), s(t_l)] = \frac{\gamma[k, l]}{\sqrt{\gamma(k, k) \times \gamma(l, l)}}$$

where $\gamma(.,.)$ is the autocovariance of the signal s . The ACF is frequently used as it is associated with several stylized facts.

As expected, the residuals are not correlated, which can be seen in figure 7.5.

Figure 7.5: ACF of GARCH Residuals

7.3 Risk measures

7.3.1 General considerations

In order to quantify risk management, we will use two risk measures. We define losses $L_t = -r_t$ in our case, as we assume we have a simple buy and hold strategy.

Value at Risk

Value at Risk can be computed as follows.

$$\text{VaR}_\alpha = \inf \{l \in \mathbb{R} : \mathbb{P}[L < l] = 1 - \alpha\} \quad (7.3)$$

It exactly represents the $(1 - \alpha)$ quantile of the losses.

Expected Shortfall

The formal definition of the Expected Shortfall is as follows:

$$\text{ES}_\alpha(L) = \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \int_\alpha^1 \text{VaR}_\beta(L) d\beta$$

where the Value at risk is defined by equation 7.3. It is however more convenient to use equation 7.4.

$$\text{ES}_\alpha = \frac{\mathbf{E}[L \mathbb{1}_{L < \alpha}]}{1 - \alpha} \quad (7.4)$$

7.3.2 Backtesting the GARCH model

We can back-test the GARCH model with historical data and monitor violations. This can be visually done using `Python 3.7` to plot the historical data on figure 7.6 [14].

Figure 7.6: GARCH(1,1) Volatility

VaR simulations

Using R, we can now back-test the VaR simulation at different confidence levels. The most common ones are 95% and 99%, and are represented on figure 7.7.

Although the fitting is not perfect, our GARCH model seems to fit historical data. We can have a closer look at violations in table 7.2.

Table 7.2: VaR Violations

	Asset A	Asset B	Asset C	Asset D
VaR 95%	4.5 %	5.8 %	5.6 %	5.6 %
VaR 99%	0.8 %	1.9 %	2.5 %	2.6 %

Figure 7.7: VaR backtesting

ES simulations

The same process can be repeated for the Expected Shortfall at 95% and 99%. In order to approximate the ES, we use the following discretization process.

$$ES_{\alpha} = \mu_A + \sigma_A \frac{\varphi(\Phi^{-1}(\alpha))}{1 - \alpha}$$

This formula utilizes the previously verified assumption that the losses follow a normal distribution. We can then compute the violations (table 7.3) and plot ES compared to absolute returns (7.8). We can notice that the percentage of violations is lower compared to VaR (table 7.2).

Table 7.3: ES Violations

	Asset A	Asset B	Asset C	Asset D
ES 95%	1.5 %	2.3 %	3.1 %	3.2 %
ES 99%	0.1 %	0.9 %	0.4 %	0.3 %

One of the features we expect to find is that ES is always larger or equal to VaR.

$$ES_{\alpha}(L) \geq VaR_{\alpha}(L), \forall \alpha \in (0, 1)$$

This inequality can be proved by using the non-decreasing property of $\alpha \mapsto \text{VaR}_\alpha(L)$.

Figure 7.8: ES backtesting

As expected, we can see in figure 7.8 that the ES is larger than the VaR.

7.3.3 Balanced portfolio expected losses

A fairly standard approach to risk management is to consider a portfolio with different assets [14]. This is particularly appropriate for foreign exchange and NDF assets as investors tend to build broad, somewhat balanced, portfolios representing their regional interests.

Definition

We can now simulate an investor with a balanced portfolio with the four NDF assets.

$$Portfolio = \sum_{i \in [a,b,c,d]} \frac{1}{4} \times Asset\ i$$

As these different assets can have non-linear dependence between their losses, we will first draw their correlograms and then simulate a Gauss copula. Gauss copulas allow us to model the dependence structure of marginal distributions.

We can first of all recall the scatter plot and the correlogram of the original log returns for the four assets (figure 7.9).

Figure 7.9: Original Log Returns Data

These samples can be transformed using the empirical cumulative distribution function we have already computed into a new sample suitable for computing the copula simulation.

Gauss copula

We will use Spearman’s rho method of moments to recover \hat{P} .

$$\rho_{Spearman} = \frac{\pi}{6} \arcsin \left(\frac{\hat{P}}{2} \right)$$

We obtain the following \hat{P} matrix.

$$\hat{P} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0000000 & 0.26433704 & 0.02329160 & -0.10653759 \\ 0.2643370 & 1.0000000 & -0.05235708 & 0.07051332 \\ 0.0232916 & -0.05235708 & 1.0000000 & -0.02900534 \\ -0.1065376 & 0.07051332 & -0.02900534 & 1.0000000 \end{bmatrix} \tag{7.5}$$

Using the `rcopula.gauss` package, we can simulate 100,000 observations to compute the Value at Risk and the Expected Shortfall, represented in table 7.4.

Table 7.4: Risk Measures for the Balanced Portfolio using Gauss Copula Simulation

	VaR	ES
95%	1.9 %	2.0 %
99%	2.0 %	2.1 %

Part III

Algorithmic Strategies

Chapter 8

Theoretical concepts

8.1 Overall Architecture

One could represent trading tools as a system with inputs, components, and outputs.

Figure 8.1: Lehalle's representation of trading tools [12]. TCA: Transaction Cost Analysis.

8.2 Backtesting

Backtesting is the idea of testing a process on past data to assess whether it would perform correctly in the future. In his book on algorithmic trading, Chan [8] insists on the importance of effective backtesting for trading algorithms, not only in order to make sure that they would perform well but also to be more efficient at designing them. Chan also refers to some common pitfalls in trading algorithms, such as look-ahead bias or bias in databases. Chan also notices that linear formulas and simple models tend to work better compared to more complex ones [8].

Chan [8] points out to several pitfalls of backtesting.

1. Look-ahead bias: using next day data by mistake to predict evolution.
2. Data-snooping bias: too many parameters fitted to specific features. Out-of-sample data should be used.
3. Survivorship data: discontinued assets or stocks or metrics can be absent of databases.

4. Venue dependence
5. Future close versus settlement prices

8.3 Popular trading strategies

8.3.1 Mean Reversion

Mean reversion is one of the most popular trading strategies. The main idea behind mean reversion strategies is to bet on the fact that the current state of the market, captured through some specific metrics such as order book imbalance or price variation, can be seen as a local extreme, and that the market will revert to an "average" state.

In his book, Chan [8] gives several examples of statistical tests to be applied on financial time series to verify the mean-reversion assumption. One of the most critical metrics in mean-reversion is the *mean-reversion half-life*, which characterizes how quickly the system reverts to its mean.

He also presents the pros and cons of such a strategy, with the ones we can apply to NDFs as summarized in table 8.1.

Table 8.1: Pros and Cons of Mean-Reversion Strategies [8]

Pros	Cons
Easy to construct	Difficult to manage the risk
Use of non-linear instruments	Strong assumptions
Work on different time scales	

In the next section, we will use mean reversion principles to derive the behavior of some metrics for our simulator. Some parallels can be drawn with the CAPM framework we described in the first part.

8.3.2 Momentum strategies

A momentum strategy is a strategy which assumes that the current market momentum will continue over time. As an example, a momentum strategy could look at how the prices currently evolve and assume that the prices will continue to go in the same direction. Chan states that there are four main causes of momentum [8].

- New information takes a long time to be processed by the market participants.
- High-frequency traders manipulate the market.
- Some trade actions are forced.
- Roll returns are persistent for futures, such as NDFs.

¹Events that come as a surprise for the whole market.

Table 8.2: Pros and Cons of Momentum Strategies [8]

Pros	Cons
Perform better in risky environments	Opposed risk and profit factors
Benefit from back swan events ¹	Crashes of momentum
Work on different time scales	

Momentum strategies can be developed to take advantage of any of these scenarios. As for mean reversion strategies, Chan also presents the pros and cons [8], summarized in table 8.2.

Chapter 9

Market impact analytics

Market impact analysis is an excellent way to monitor the performance of an execution algorithm. As seen in the first section and Lehalle's book [12], the CAPM model is a very popular framework to model market impact. We will discuss market impact modelization for our algorithms, although it is to measure it since financial data tends to be very noisy. There are several metrics which can be used.

1. Price delta by the time elapsed
2. Tick frequency by the time elapsed
3. Order book imbalance by the time elapsed

The first item can be used with equation 1.2 from Lehalle's book [12].

$$\text{Market Impact} \simeq K \times \text{Duration}^\alpha \times \text{PLR}^\gamma \quad (1.2)$$

9.1 Price delta evolution

We can simulate market impact according to equation 1.2. In our case, we will make the following assumption, based on our observations in part 1.

$$\text{PLR}_{\text{AssetA}} = 0.1$$

$$\text{PLR}_{\text{AssetB}} = 0.2$$

$$\text{PLR}_{\text{AssetC}} = 0.5$$

$$\text{PLR}_{\text{AssetD}} = 0.2$$

Indeed, based on the average top of book liquidity and the minimum order size on the market, we could derive the PLR for several currency pairs.

It is then easy to calibrate α and γ on high-frequency market data and to compare it with our trades to assess our impact on the price change.

9.2 Tick frequency evolution

Tick frequency evolution is an interesting parameter to study, as one may expect that the point process representing a market action is self-exciting.

One of the most common representations of such a process is a Hawkes process [4, 13]. As one can complete a statistical analysis of such processes, a median and an average time can be derived for further modellisation.

9.3 Order book imbalance

Order book imbalance is one of the most straightforward metrics to monitor but is also one of the noisiest. We can very intuitively derive the following "relaxation" model for order book imbalance, represented on figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: Ideal Market Impact of a trade on Order Book Imbalance

Although it is tough to verify this assumption, we can model the following, inspired by the CAPM and other metrics.

Definition 9.1 (Modelling Market Impact on Order Book Imbalance). *Let $OBI_{\mu}(t)$ the systematic order book imbalance at t in the portfolio, were $t = 0$ at the moment of the trade. Let $\alpha \in [0, 1[$ be the relaxation coefficient modeling the ability of the market to absorb the order impact.*

$$OBI(t) = OBI_{\mu}(t) + k \times \alpha^t$$

$k \in \mathbb{R}$ and is specific to the trade.

Note that in definition 9.1, we do not make any assumption on the systematic order book imbalance.

9.4 Building a simulator

One of the most critical steps when designing algorithms in finance is to backtest and to simulate them. Building a simulator is a complex process, and the different simulations detailed in this chapter are commonly used to derive some features in the simulator.

Generally speaking, a simulator has a structure (figure 9.2) that includes:

- Models: the underlying models for the market response, as described above.
- Test Strategy; the strategy we want to test.
- Market data: selected market data, matching the models.

It is not very interesting to simulate the model over extensive periods of time, as back-testing should be enough to make sure the model performs well under normal conditions. Scenarios are used to "stress-test" the model, in moments of very low liquidity or of high price deltas.

Figure 9.2: General Structure for a Market Simulator

For NDFs, a simulator should be calibrated on NDF market data to simulate how a trading strategy operates.

Chapter 10

Designing algorithms

Now we have studied the theoretical construction of a financial algorithm. We can now more precisely describe the structure for such an algorithm that would be specific to the NDFs.

Several algorithm architectures can be used, but the most frequent one is the linear - or cascade - pattern (figure 8.1), as described by Lehalle [12] and by Chan [8]. The main reason for the popularity of such architecture is that it is the easiest to implement and to maintain, especially with regards to synchronization with the market.

10.1 Input and output

In this section, we will describe the main characteristics we expect from the signals in our algorithms. Note that all the metrics described in the first part of this thesis were designed to be used as such signals.

10.1.1 Input signals

The first step is to define the input signals we will use in our algorithms. Most of the input signals are driven by market data we receive. Among the most common market signals are order book imbalance and price variation. Several of the metrics described in part 1 can be used to derive signals for the algorithm itself.

We can, however, point to several common characteristics these signals must have:

- Reliable: the information is accurate and unambiguous;
- Well defined: signals should be bounded and defined at every time stamp, especially with regards to machine learning models.

Note that there may be a loop-back as the output signal, or the execution feedback can also be used as inputs. In that case, they must also comply with the standards stated above.

10.1.2 Output signals

The output signals may vary depending on the context. For NDFs, there must be at least the following information.

- Action: buy or sell
- Price
- Volume
- Time

10.2 Reducing market impact

A common factor in finance is that market participants want to reduce their impact. This can be done in different ways, including the following.

- Over the counter trades
- Iceberg orders on the market

10.2.1 Over the counter

OTC¹ trades are trades done directly between two market participants and are not immediately made public². This allows executing large amounts without disrupting the venues. The main downside to OTC trading is the lack of transparency and guarantees between the two agents. This is a significant issue with regards to algorithmic execution, as the chain of events is contained in a very narrow time frame.

10.2.2 Iceberg orders

Iceberg orders are commonly used by traders to place large amounts on trading venues. Say one wants to execute thirteen million NDFs on an order book which only has eight. When the iceberg order is placed, only one million is displayed to the other market participants in the updated order book.

This entails two main consequences:

- It is more difficult to assess how quickly one's order is processed, as the price-time priority is less explicit;
- most importantly, there exists some *hidden liquidity* which is difficult to model and to capture, but which has an impact on the dynamics of the market.

¹Over the counter

²This mode of execution is now regulated under MiFID II.

10.3 Compliance and regulation

One of the most critical aspects of using algorithms in finance is to make sure they will operate correctly and according to the rules. In-house compliance officers check proper operation while the regulatory framework is set up by the FCA³ [2].

10.3.1 Compliance

Compliance is the division inside a financial institution which makes sure regulations, and internal design policies are implemented. Specific processes are required, such as testing the strategies over some scenarios.

10.3.2 Regulation

Here is a non-exhaustive list of the requirements by the FCA [2].

- A kill switch must be implemented in the program. This switch must also allow canceling all unexecuted orders when it is triggered.
- Monitoring the algorithm before (pre-trade controls), during (real-time controls) and after (post-trade controls) execution.
- Systems must be fully tested, and an independent assessment must be carried internally.

These requirements come in addition to the necessity to provide theoretical, mainly mathematical support, for the algorithm. As the algorithm is created, these elements are taken into consideration at every stage of the development process.

³Financial Conduct Authority

Postface

In this thesis, we focused on the Non-Deliverable Forwards market and studied their market microstructure. We derived from this study risk management strategies, such as a way to price NDFs using Vasicek and CIR simulations. We have also used GARCH modeling for volatility, which led to satisfying results. Finally, we presented concepts and suggestions for algorithm design.

Our pricing relies on endogenous models, so it would be interesting to try using exogenous models, such as CIR++ or Black-Karasinski. The interest rate of the investor should also be modeled separately, as the price formula for NDFs depends on the investor's local interest rate.

The NDF market is evolving very quickly, and a wider range of market dynamics can be captured to create more accurate and more reliable models.

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